

Spatial Quantum Entropy

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In the literature, Shannon's entropy with spatial density as probability i.e. $\text{density}(x)$ $\ln(\text{density}(x))$ appears frequently. It seems, however, that this calculation of entropy assumes no knowledge of momentum, yet $\text{density} = W(x)W^*(x)$ (for a bound state) where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In other words, the wavefunction $W(x)$ contains information about the momentum distribution associated with $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$.

In classical statistical mechanics, entropy is calculated using $\exp[-(p^2/2m + V(x))/T]$ which includes both momentum and spatial considerations. In a previous note (1), we calculated a possible expression for entropy using $P(p/x)P(x)$. This includes Shannon's spatial entropy and other terms even if one sums over p after forming Shannon's entropy with $P(p/x)P(x)$. In this note, we try to consider the interpretation of these two forms of entropy.

Shannon's Spatial Entropy in Quantum Mechanics

One often sees in the literature a form proportional to $\text{density}(x) \ln[\text{density}(x)]$ for quantum entropy of a system represented by a wavefunction (with $\text{density}(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$). This is Shannon's entropy, so one may ask: What is its interpretation? Shannon's entropy seems to be based on arrangements of objects each with probability P_i . Thus, if there are N objects (with N very large), the probability related to an object i is $P_i^{N_i}$, but $N_i = N P_i$ (for very large N) in this case. Thus, the logarithm of the overall probability for such a scenario is:

$$\ln [\text{Product over } i \ P_i^{N_i}] = \sum \text{over } i \ N_i \ln(P_i) \quad ((1)) \text{ or Shannon's entropy}$$

This is equivalent to considering all possible arrangements of N_i objects and writing 1 over the sum of this number and then taking the \ln :

$$\ln [1 / \{ N! / \text{Product over } i \ (N_i)! \}] \text{ is proportional to: } \sum \text{over } i \ P_i \ln(P_i)$$

If one uses $\text{density}(x)$, the quantum spatial density, as probability, one considers the position of (say a bound particle) at different times with no information whatsoever about momentum. In other words $P(x_i) = \text{density}(x_i)$ and one considers arrangements of different positions of a particle at different times. It should be noted that $\text{density}(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction $= \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Momentum may be positive or negative in this sum, and $W(x)$ is related to a conditional probability $P(p/x)$ distribution. Thus, a particle may move forward from t_1 to t_2 , but then move back to x at t_3 . What is unusual is that Shannon's form allows for a particle to be at x at t_1 and also to be at x at t_2 . A particle has momentum and so should move. If one allows $t_2 - t_1$ to be of a certain length to allow for at least two stochastic hits from a potential, then a particle may move forward and backward by the same amount during $t_2 - t_1$ and so could be at

x at both t1 and t2. An alternative is to consider the particle as having momentum 0 at x and no stochastic hit occurring, although this is very restrictive.

Thus, if one considers a quantum particle as having probability density(x)=P(x) to be at x, one may create a Shannon's entropy density(x) ln[density(x)] by considering different position arrangements (at different times) and by ignoring momentum completely. The question then becomes: Should one ignore momentum? In this note, we try to argue that for a quantum system it seems one should not.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

In classical statistical mechanics, one also has a spatial density proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ i.e. constant for $V(x)=\text{constant}$, yet one does not create a Shannon's entropy based on density alone. Expressions for the entropy are related to derivatives of the partition function which considers both $\exp[-(p^2/2m + V(x))/T]$. Thermal motion is critical to entropy in statistical mechanics. In fact in a gas, one has particles scattering with each other in elastic collisions. Thus, if reaction balance is governed by: $g(f(e1)) g(f(e2)) = g(f(e3)) g(f(e4))$ with $e1+e2=e3+e4$, where g is a function based on scattering rules and f(ei) the energy distribution, then:

$$\ln(g(f(ei))) = - (ei-u)/T \text{ where } u \text{ is the chemical potential and } T \text{ the temperature} \quad ((2))$$

Kaniadiakis (2) suggests one may create a generalized entropy using:

$$\text{Integral } df \ln(g(f(ei))) \quad ((3))$$

Thus, entropy is linked directly to collision kinematics. For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, $g=1$ whereas for fermions and bosons, $g = f / (1 \pm f)$. In a quantum problem, a particle receives stochastic hits from a potential, thus one might expect that entropy should be related to more than spatial arrangements.

Alternative Quantum Mechanical Entropy as Presented in (1)

In (1), we suggested that instead of using P(x) in Shannon's entropy, one may use $P(p/x)P(x)$ which incorporates information about momentum and position. It may be noted that $\sum P(p/x) = 1$ and $\int P(x) dx = 1$. Then:

$$\text{Shannon's entropy is proportional to: } P(p/x) P(x) [\ln(P(x)) + \ln(P(p/x))] \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Where } P(x) = W^*(x)W(x) \text{ and } P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((4))$$

Then: Shannon's quantum entropy is proportional to (for a bound state):

$$P(p/x) P(x) \ln(P(x)) + P(p/x) WW \{ \ln(a(p)) + ipx - \ln(W) \}$$

Summing over p yields: $\frac{1}{2} P(x) \ln(P(x)) + \int W \sum_p a(p) \ln(a(p)) \exp(ipx) + W \frac{d}{dx} W$ (5)

(If one integrates over x, the second term becomes: $\sum_p a(p)a(-p) \ln(a(p))$
 For $a(p)=a(-p)$, one has $\frac{1}{2} P(p) \ln(P(p))$ where $P(p)= \sum_x a(p)a(x)$ for $a(p)$ real

Thus, the entropy from (1) is $\frac{1}{2}$ the Shannon's spatial entropy plus $\frac{1}{2}$ Shannon's momentum entropy (for $a(p)=a(-p)$) plus a term $W \frac{d}{dx} W$. This differs from $P(x) \ln(P(x))$ spatial entropy and seems to contain information about momentum as well as position.

Interpretation of the Entropy from (1)

If Shannon's spatial quantum entropy $P(x) \ln[P(x)]$ is related to positional arrangements of the bound quantum object in time, what does $P(p/x)P(x) \ln [P(p/x)P(x)]$ describe? It seems there is a probability to have a p_i at x_j , thus one considers all pairs of (p_i, x_j) in this new entropy. Thus, it is not surprising that the result is different. To see the difference consider a very simple example: $P(x_1)=\frac{1}{3}$ $P(x_2)=\frac{2}{3}$ $P(p_1/x_1)=\frac{1}{4}$ $P(p_2/x_1)=\frac{3}{4}$ $P(p_1/x_2)=\frac{2}{5}$ $P(p_2/x_2)=\frac{3}{5}$.

The usual spatial entropy yields $-\frac{1}{3} \ln(\frac{1}{3}) - \frac{2}{3} \ln(\frac{2}{3})$ whereas the entropy from (1) gives:

$$-\frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{4}) \ln(\frac{1}{12}) - \frac{1}{3}(\frac{3}{4}) \ln(\frac{3}{4}) - \frac{2}{3}(\frac{2}{5}) \ln(\frac{4}{15}) - \frac{2}{3}(\frac{3}{5}) \ln(\frac{6}{5})$$

Thus in the second case, one considers different t_i points represented by (x_i, p_j) with $P(x_i)$ related to the probability to be at x_i and $P(p_j/x_i)$ related to the probability to have p_j at x_i . To be at x_i and have p_j , the probability is then: $P(x_i) P(p_j/x_i)$. Summing over p as shown above yields $\frac{1}{2} P(x) \ln(P(x))$, but other x related terms. We think it is important to stress that a momentum distribution (related to $P(p/x)$ is contained within $W(x)$, thus density $\rho(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ does not just represent spatial information. We thus argue it may be problematic to consider only spatial Shannon's entropy and eliminate all information about momentum.

It should be noted that there exist hydrodynamical derivations in the literature (3 and others) which are based solely on the classical idea of spatial density. A Schrodinger equation is obtained as a function of this density (and in some cases of a classical velocity field S). The wavefunction is introduced solely through a variable change $W(x)= \sqrt{P(x)} \exp(iS/\hbar)$. Thus, in such a scenario it seems one does not need focus at all on a momentum distribution contained within $W(x)$. In such a case, one might be tempted to proceed to compute $P(x) \ln(P(x))$ as Shannon's entropy, but we argue for a result based on probability = $P(p/x)P(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ represents a momentum distribution associated with $P(p/x)$. Thus, spatial density $\rho(x)= W^*(x)W(x)$ contains information about momentum as well as position. We thus argue that it may not be a good idea

to use Shannon's spatial entropy proportional to $P(x) \ln[P(x)]$ as it ignores this momentum content. We propose a quantum entropy given by: $-.5 P(x) \ln(P(x)) + W \frac{d}{dx} W + W \sum_{p} a(p) \ln(a(p) \exp(ipx))$. The last term becomes $-.5 P(p) \ln(P(p))$ when integrated over p if $a(p)=a(-p)$. This entropy is based on using $P(p/x) P(x)$ as probability instead of $P(x)$.

References

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